

Solving Large Scale Fission Surface Power Reactor Shielding Problems

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803193

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a demonstration of a shielding analysis for a sample Fission Surface Power (FSP) reactor using the PENTRAN (S_N) driven Forward Consistent Adjoint Driven Importance Sampling (FW-CADIS) methodology, applied to an MCNP6.3 FSP shielding model. The results indicate that performing a full-system simulation remains computationally intensive and time-consuming for large-scale shielding evaluations such as FSP fenceline dose assessments. While the FW-CADIS approach provides a reasonable speedup in dose rate estimation, the analysis also reveals that radiation from lunar regolith dominates the dose rate in regions away from the reactor shielding surface, particularly in the direction of the planned lunar habitat.

Keywords: Fission Surface Power, Dose Rate Evaluation, PENTRAN, CADIS, FW-CADIS

1. INTRODUCTION

With the renewed global interest in nuclear energy and the surge of industrial activity surrounding the modern nuclear renaissance, radiation shielding is considered a critical safety design factor for microreactors and Fission Surface Power (FSP) systems. These designs typically exhibit power outputs ranging from several hundred kilowatts (kW_{th}) up to 20 megawatts (MW_{th}) [1], with several concepts specifically engineered for modular deployment using standard semi-truck trailers [1]. The power levels of these microreactors, including FSP reactor designs, are comparable to those of TRIGA (Training, Research, Isotope Production, General Atomic) reactors [2], which generally require a minimum of 20 feet of water shielding for effective radiation attenuation. Consequently, microreactors must meet stringent shielding performance requirements to ensure compliance with regulatory fenceline dose limits. Historical microreactor design data indicates a dose rate of approximately 15 mR/hr at 25 ft forward direction after 24 hours from reactor shutdown [3]. Additional literature suggests that radiation levels at a human habitat located 1 km from the reactor should not exceed 5 rem/yr [4].

Due to the above considerations, modeling these systems results in large-scale, deep-penetration transport problems that are computationally demanding when using full-core neutron and photon source simulations. This paper presents an analysis of a sample FSP reactor shielding problem using MCNP6.3 [5]. The workflow integrates the PENTRAN three-dimensional, parallel, hybrid discrete ordinate (S_N)/Method of Characteristic (MOC) ray-tracing code [6,7] for importance function generation, the WWPEN2MC utility [8] for establishing lower weight-window bounds [5] and MCNP 6.3 for executing Monte Carlo transport simulations. The results will demonstrate the appropriateness of this

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methodology for solving the complex shielding challenges inherent to compact microreactor systems. A simplified hydrogen model (H-model) derived from a space reactor shielding benchmark problem originally developed by Knolls Atomic Power Laboratory (KAPL) [9] is utilized in this study for demonstration purposes.

2. Model Description

In this section, the PENTRAN 3D S_N model used for calculating the importance function and the MCNP6.3 Constructive Solid Geometry (CSG) model used for dose rate calculation are discussed in Sections 2.1 and 2.2, respectively. The lunar regolith composition is discussed in Section 2.3.

2.1. MCNP6.3 Simplified H-Model

The MCNP6.3 simplified H-model corresponding to the material and boundary conditions are shown in Figure 1. The dimensions of this model are 500 cm \times 500 cm \times 2000 cm in x, y, and z directions respectively. The detailed surface moon power reactor dimension is described in Table 1. The dosimeter is placed at $x=1975.0$ cm, $y=0.0$ cm, $z=0.0$ cm. Table I further shows the detailed simplified H-model reactor and shielding dimensions. The cross-section library used in the MCNP6.3 model is ENDF/B-VII.1 evaluated at room temperature (300 K). The lunar atmosphere density is assumed to be 10^{-12} g/cc. Spatially uniform Watt fission spectrum from ^{235}U is assumed in the homogenized reactor core [5].

Figure 1. MCNP6.3 Simplified H-Model Axial Projection

Table I. H-model Reactor and Shielding Dimensions.

Item	Radius (cm)	Axial Height/Thickness (cm)
Reactor Core	24.25	59.50
Graphite Reflector	37.25	13.00
Lunar Air Gap	55.75	14.65
Beryllium Lining	60.75	5
Boron Carbide	76.75	16
Tungsten	78.75	2
Lithium Hydride	133.75	55

2.2. PENTRAN Simplified H-Model

In this work, the Consistent Adjoint Driven Importance Sampling (CADIS) methodology [10] is employed for variance reduction, as the 16 cm thick B₄C shield substantially attenuates the neutron flux from the reactor core. PENTRAN is utilized as the importance function generator for this study, and the corresponding geometry and meshing configuration are illustrated in *Figure 2*. Consistent with the MCNP6.3 CSG model, all component dimensions are identical, except for discretization truncation errors inherent to the PENTRAN mesh representation. PENTRAN version 9.43e supports hybrid discrete ordinates (S_N) and method-of-characteristics (MOC) ray-tracing calculations. In this problem setup, coarse mesh regions containing air employ MOC ray tracing, while other coarse mesh regions are solved using the S_N method with a quadrature order of S₁₂ and a Legendre polynomial P₁ anisotropic scattering expansion. The BUGLE96 47-group neutron cross-section library [11] is used for the importance function calculations, with a neutron importance convergence tolerance set to 10⁻³.

Figure 2. MCNP6.3 Simplified H-Model Axial Projection (Green is lunar atmosphere)

2.3. Lunar Regolith Composition

The NASA Lunar Regolith Simulant User's Guide Rev. A [12] provides the foundation for estimating lunar soil composition. "Regolith," unlike terrestrial soil, refers to loose surface material on the Moon and is reproduced on Earth using simulants for equipment and mobility testing. Section 4 of the Ref. [12] compares these simulants with Apollo, Luna, and Chang'e mission samples, summarizing mineralogy, chemical composition, and density data. The guide classifies regolith into mare (dark basaltic plains) and highland (light anorthositic) regions. Eight major oxides - representing 99.84 wt% of the surface - define the bulk composition. Trace elements below 0.1 wt% [13,14] are excluded here due to negligible radiological impact. Prior transport studies for shielding and surface radiation analyses [15,16,17] likewise rely on these eight-oxide models, drawing data from NASA and related sources [18,19]. Natural isotopic abundances are assumed, with minor lunar deviations (e.g., a known -1% in K-39/K-41) judged insignificant [20,21,22]. *Table II* lists elemental atomic abundances derived by averaging mare and highland compositions and normalizing to 100%. The density data is similarly known to vary slightly with depth, and its effect is under investigation. However, for these models an average value of 1.77 g/cm³ is assumed.

Table II. Lunar Regolith Suggested Composition.

Element	Atom Fraction	Weight Fraction	Element	Atom Fraction	Weight Fraction
O	0.61	0.44	Si	0.17	0.21
Na	3×10^{-3}	3.1×10^{-3}	Ca	4.9×10^{-2}	8.9×10^{-2}
Mg	4.7×10^{-2}	5.1×10^{-2}	Ti	6.9×10^{-3}	1.5×10^{-2}
Al	8.2×10^{-2}	1.0×10^{-2}	Fe	3.8×10^{-2}	9.4×10^{-2}

3. PENTRAN-calculated Importance Function

The PENTRAN calculated importance function is shown in *Figure 3*, with importance/adjoint source in the dosimeter. It is used to define the MCNP6.3 lower weight window bounds calculations, which are calculated as follows:

$$w_l(\vec{r}, E) = \frac{R}{\phi^+(\vec{r}, E)} \frac{2}{(C_u + 1)} \quad (1)$$

where $w_l(\vec{r}, E)$ is space and energy dependent lower weight window bounds, R is the approximated detector response $\phi^+(\vec{r}, E)$ is the space and energy dependent adjoint/importance function, and C_u is the ratio between higher and lower weight window bounds.

Figure 3. PENTRAN Material Map (top) and Importance Function Axial Projection Map (bottom) - Neutron Energy of 0.11 MeV to 0.18 MeV

In deterministic models of such large scale characterized by low density materials, ray effect [23] is typically observed if using the S_N method on its own. Thanks to the use of MOC ray tracing in the low-density regions, ray effect is not observed in the PENTRAN solution, even within the extremely optically thin regions used to model the lunar atmosphere (almost vacuum). However, literature has indicated that the CADIS methodology can suffer in presence of large low-density regions, such as air, presented [24]. The authors of this work have observed similar performance issues. The relatively flat importance function trend in such regions can even worsen the performance of the CADIS methodology with respect to the analog solution. Note that flat energy dependent adjoint source is used. Therefore, we decided to employ the FW-CADIS methodology for two reasons: (1) Alleviation of ray effect without using the characteristic ray tracing; and (2) A more generic variance reduction for global dose rate evaluation. The same PENTRAN importance model is modified to include a global adjoint/importance source (*Figure 4*, red material) using a non-fully converged MCNP 47 BUGLE energy group track length estimator flux tally as the adjoint/importance source. Note, with respect to *Figure 3*, the adjoint source for this model is located in the entire lunar atmosphere rather than just the dosimeter.

The corresponding importance function solution from energy range of 0.11 to 0.18 MeV is also presented in *Figure 4*.

Figure 4. PENTRAN Material Map (Top) and Importance Function Axial Projection Map (bottom) - Neutron Energy of 0.11 MeV to 0.18 MeV

As shown in *Figure 4*, the dominant contributor to the total radiation dose originates from the lunar regolith, rather than from direct dispersion at the FSP reactor shielding surface. The regolith region shows significantly higher values compared to all other regions.

4. Dose Rate Calculation with MCNP6.3

In this section, we present a comparison of dose rate calculations performed using MCNP6.3, both with and without the application of weight window variance reduction derived from the PENTRAN-calculated importance function, as illustrated in *Figure 4*. All dose rates were computed, assuming a neutron source strength of 10^{16} neutrons per second from the reactor core and using the ANSI/ANS (1977) flux-to-dose conversion factors [5] for the neutron dose estimation.

4.1. MCNP6.3 Analog Solution

The MCNP6.3 analog solution dose rate map, shown in *Figure 5*, along with the corresponding relative 1σ statistical uncertainties. The results show a dose rate of approximately 276 rem/hr at the detector location around $x=19.75$ meters. In this calculation, no variance reduction technique is used. The total CPU computational time is 5331.75 minutes using 10^8 histories, on 104 CPUs. Note that the dimensions shown in the figure use different scales for the x and z directions.

4.2. Use of FW-CADIS for Variance Reduction

By using the global weight windows calculated as shown in Section 3, the same problem is rerun with 10^9 histories and $C_u = 5$. *Figure 6* shows the corresponding dose map and 1 relative statistical

uncertainty. The total computational time is 1035.85 minutes CPU time and 10 times less in number of histories than the analog MCNP calculation.

Figure 5. Analog MCNP Solution; Left: Dose rate in mrem/hr; Right: 1σ relative statistical uncertainties

Figure 6. MCNP Solution with FW-CADIS; Left: Dose rate (mrem/hr); Right: 1σ rel. statistical uncertainties

To provide a better quantitative comparison, dose rates at the dosimeter shown in Figure 1 and 2 are provided in Table III. The Figure of Merit (FOM) of the MCNP6.3 calculations [5] is calculated based on the following formula:

$$FOM = \frac{1}{\sigma^2 T} \quad (2)$$

where σ is the relative statistical uncertainty, while T is total computational time, which is inversely proportional to the square root of the number of histories.

Table III. Dosimeter Dose Rate Comparison.

Item	Analog MCNP6.3	FW-CADIS MCNP6.3
Dose Rate	276.50 mrem/hr	276.26 mrem/hr
Relative 1σ	0.92%	1.86%
FOM	6.2	5.3
Number of Histories	10^8	10^9
CPU Time	5331.75 minutes	1035.85 minutes

A factor of 5 speedup is achieved using the FW-CADIS methodology. The FOM values reported in *Table III* are taken directly from the MCNP output for the total neutron flux at the dosimeter location. Dose rates are calculated by multiplying the energy group dependent neutron flux with the ANSI (1977) neutron flux-to-dose conversion factors, and scaled using a source strength of 10^{16} neutrons/sec.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this preliminary study, we demonstrated an approach that integrates PENTRAN and MCNP6.3 through the FW-CADIS methodology to accelerate dose rate evaluations for the FSP reactor. The FW-CADIS method provides a factor of 5 computational speedup for large-scale dose rate analyses, particularly in models containing extensive optically thin regions. Notably, most of the dose rate on the lunar surface near the human habitat results from neutron transport through the lunar regolith, rather than from direct dispersion through the reactor shielding surface. Future work will involve the use of MCNP6.3 Surface Source Write (SSW) and Surface Source Read (SSR) cards and a two-stage problem partitioning strategy to further improve computational efficiency, as well as studying problems in detail. In addition, we plan to investigate the influence of lunar regolith composition on the resulting dose distribution and assess potential mitigation strategies to further reduce the surface dose.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work is supported by the internal fund from the University of Utah Nuclear Engineering Program, CVEEN Department. We also acknowledge the contributions of the Utah Center for High Performance Computing (UCHPC). All MCNP6.3 computations were performed on the REDWOOD cluster at the UCHPC 'critcel-rw' partition, partially supported by the NIH shared instrumentation grant 1S10OD021644-01A1. All PENTRAN calculations were performed on the NOTCHPEAK cluster "civil-np" partition at UCHPC.

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